

Working Towards End-To-End Trustworthiness

CORENEXT

Building a trustworthy-by-design computing platform for 6G flagship use cases to consolidate European digital sovereignty and unlock a new economic perspective.

Meet some of the **CORENEXT** women

Parisa Aghdam

Sabine Oeste

Anastasia Grebenyuk

Laura Wetsch

Jian Yiyun

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COREnext Women Campaigns

On International Women's Day and Women and Girls in Science Day, the COREnext project organized campaigns to highlight and recognize the valuable contributions made by women within the project. Let's introduce you to a few of the remarkable women involved in COREnext!

- **Sabine Oeste**
- **Parisa Aghdamam**
- **Anastasia Grebenyuk**
- **Jian Yiyun**
- **Laura Wetsch**

**The Crucial Role of
Privacy in
Automotive
Infrastructure**

The number of connected vehicles in the automotive industry has experienced a notable rise. Let's delve into one of the COREnext use cases to gain a deeper understanding of this phenomenon.

Securing IoT Systems

The IoT is revolutionizing various industries by connecting devices and leveraging data to propel technological progress. Discover more about the transformative impact of IoT on verticals!

COREnext will be featured at the EuCnC

6G is envisaged to impact the consumer market in addition to the enterprise market beyond what is accomplished by 5G today. Connected factory floors and smart businesses will be accompanied by fully connected and intelligent consumer ecosystems. However, for this evolution to happen, trust must be earned among users and supported by innovative design. Come and visit us on the **8th of June at 11:00 CEST**.

[Learn more](#)

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